

Salinity stress tolerance in camelina: A focus on the germination stage for crop improvement

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ABSTRACT

Camelina is gaining recognition as a promising alternative crop due to its high seed oil content and as a potential salt tolerant crop on marginal land not suitable for major commodities. This research aimed to evaluate the impact of varying salinity levels and different types of salt on the germination process of camelina, investigating the physiological, morphometric, and biochemical mechanisms underlying salinity tolerance. Seeds from two spring genotypes, NS Slatka and NS Zlatka, were subjected to salinity stress through saline solutions of sodium chloride (NaCl) and sodium sulfate (Na₂SO₄) at concentrations of 50, 100, 150, and 200 mM. Salinity levels of 150 mM and above negatively impacted most of the surveyed parameters, with Na₂SO₄ causing a more pronounced detrimental effect than NaCl. In general, NS Slatka was more sensitive to both tested salts in terms of germination and seedling growth parameters than NS Zlatka. At the same time, it exhibited greater stability under stressful conditions concerning leaf dimensions, suggesting the possibility of different mechanisms for tolerating salt stress. As for root weight and seedling length, NS Zlatka demonstrated a slightly better tolerance to Na₂SO₄ compared to NaCl. Proline accumulation was higher in NS Zlatka, particularly under Na₂SO₄ stress, indicating that this genotype may employ more efficient mechanisms to mitigate salt-induced stress. The high germination recovery rate (exceeding 40 % for both genotypes under the tested salt type) indicated that salinity only has a temporary effect on camelina seed germination, which can suggest interesting applications in soils affected by salinity fluctuation. The results of this study underscored the importance of understanding responses to different salt types and levels of stress, to identify the most suitable camelina genotypes to different salt-affected areas.

1. Introduction

The global scientific community has dedicated extensive efforts to exploring alternative plant energy sources for a long time. A plant species that is gaining more attention as a promising option is false flax, scientifically known as camelina (*Camelina sativa* L. Crantz). It is grown for its nutrient-dense seed oil, abundant in omega-3 fatty acids, which makes it a prized resource for both animal and human diets (Matteo et al., 2023). In addition to its use as a functional food, camelina has significant industrial applications, with authorities in both Europe and the United States designating it as a strategic crop for energy production (Arshad et al., 2022). Camelina oil can also serve as an oleochemical in various non-food industries (cosmetic, medical supplies, biofuels, the production of bioplastics, biodegradable lubricants and surfactants)

(Cerone and Smith, 2021). Even after oil extraction, the leftover seed cake remains abundant in valuable nutritional compounds. Besides, growing market demand for bio-based products in the renewable fuel sector, along with enhancements in cost efficiency, is expected to enhance future demand for this climate-resilient crop (Neupane et al., 2022).

Camelina is also regarded as one of the most suitable options for marginal land in Europe. This is particularly relevant in the context of the European bioeconomy's focus on sustainable growth through the search for and development of bio-based raw materials that can substitute fossil resources, with an emphasis on industrial crops (Zanetti et al., 2024). Known for its resilience to drought and low temperatures, camelina has a relatively short growing cycle, making it suitable as a rotational crop (Sainger et al., 2017) or a cover crop to enhance soil

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health and mitigate erosion (Meyer et al., 2019; Zanetti et al., 2021). It can also be labelled as an environmentally friendly option as it requires fewer inputs such as water, fertilizers, and pesticides compared to other oilseed crops (Kukrić et al., 2022; Ghidoli et al., 2023). The seed faces numerous challenges throughout its production, storage, and quality preservation phases (Adetunji et al., 2021). The success of its survival and response depends on the ability to withstand ongoing abiotic and biotic stresses. Understanding how various stresses influence seed germination is crucial, as abiotic stresses can affect this process by affecting the imbibition phase, rupture of testa, and causing oxidative harm to reserves of protein and starch (Shahzad et al., 2022). Salinity is one of the most significant abiotic stresses affecting the share of agricultural land. Soil salinization, affecting about 10 % of the Earth's land surface (FAO, 2021), is a pervasive global issue caused by natural geochemical processes and human activities (Singh, 2022). Primary salinization is caused by factors such as atmospheric deposition, sea level rise, wind blow and increasing temperatures, which have significantly affected extensive areas of cultivated land (Das and Biswas, 2022). Salt stress primarily arises from neutral salts such as NaCl and Na₂SO₄ in natural field surroundings. NaCl is commonly found in the soil in different regions, and in addition, the presence of specific cations such as K⁺, Ca²⁺ and Mg²⁺, together with their associated anions such as Cl⁻, NO₃⁻ and SO₄²⁻, significantly affects seed germination and growth (Zehra et al., 2015). Additionally, secondary salinization, which affects an estimated 30 % of irrigated lands, is exacerbated by excessive fertilizer use, inadequate management practices, and intensified agricultural activities of deforestation and overgrazing. This dual origin of salinization poses a substantial threat to agricultural productivity and ecosystem conditions worldwide (Hopmans et al., 2021, Das and Biswas, 2022).

The presence of salt in soil impedes the germination process through multiple complex mechanisms. It creates osmotic stress because salt ions attract water molecules, leading to reduced water uptake and disrupting seed hydration (Duarte and Souza, 2016, Stavi et al., 2021). High salt concentrations can lead to ion toxicity impairing cellular functions and enzyme activities essential for germination. This combination of effects can significantly delay or inhibit the germination and early growth of seedlings (Isayenkov and Maathuis., 2019, Reguera et al., 2020). In addition to the factors mentioned, salt also causes damage to the seed embryo and reduces the availability of adenosine triphosphate (ATP) and stored metabolites, which are essential for the normal development of the germination process (Rajjou et al., 2012). In other words, salt stress negatively impacts plant growth in various ways through different stages, including impaired seed germination and morphometric changes such as stunted growth and chlorosis ultimately leading to plant decay or reduced yield. It also affects physiological processes like photosynthesis and nutrient absorption, along with biochemical alterations that lead to oxidative stress, electrolyte leakage, and disorganization of cellular membranes (Hannachi et al., 2022). Since seeds are most vulnerable and sensitive to environmental factors during germination, this can be considered a key phase during stressful conditions such as salinity.

Besides the evaluation of seeds based on their germination rates under salt stress, the potential of seeds to recover and germinate successfully when more favorable conditions occur after salt stress exposure is very important for practical application -in salt affected soils where variable salinity is present. This is commonly seen in coastal regions, where saltwater intrusion into freshwater sources occurs during periods of drought (Tarolli et al., 2023) causing temporary changes in groundwater levels (He et al., 2014). Furthermore, human activities—such as using irrigation water with high salt content—combined with variations in precipitation, often contribute to rapid changes in soil salinity (Zhang et al., 2024). In these situations, the capacity of seeds to properly germinate when optimal conditions are restored could be considered a favorable trait for crop cultivation. As soil salinization becomes an increasing problem and demand for bio-based feedstocks rises, understanding camelina's tolerance to this abiotic stress is crucial, given its

potential as a valuable industrial crop. Although there are several studies on the influence of salinity stress on germination dynamics and the general response of camelina to such conditions, many unknowns remain. These include the specific biochemical pathways that confer salinity tolerance within camelina populations, the threshold levels of salinity that can be tolerated, and how salinity interacts with other abiotic stresses, such as drought or temperature extremes. By assessing these thresholds, scientists can better evaluate the tolerance of different species to saline environments, which is crucial for agricultural planning and ecological conservation. This research aimed to evaluate how varying levels of salinity and different types of salt affected the germination process of camelina seeds. The present study investigated the possible physiological, morphometric and biochemical mechanisms that enabled this species to tolerate salinity during germination.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Camelina seed sources and salinity treatments

Seeds from the camelina spring genotypes NS Slatka and NS Zlatka, produced in 2023 at the Institute of Field and Vegetable Crops in Novi Sad, Serbia (Rimski šančevi, 45°31' N, 19°82' E, 82 m a.s.l.), were used in the present study. The seeds were produced under agronomical management for this crop under specific agroecological conditions. The conductivity of the ionic solutions was calculated, with NaCl showing values of 5.6, 10.6, 15.4, and 20 mS/m, and Na₂SO₄ showing values of 9.7, 18.1, 25.8, and 33.3 mS/m at 25°C. These saline solutions were then used as germination media to create varying levels of salinity stress.

2.2. Germination assay and assessment of seedling morphometric traits

The germination assay followed the ISTA protocol (2024) with slight modifications. Firstly, seeds were surface sterilised using a 2 % NaClO solution for 1 minute. Three replicates of 100 seeds each were sown in Petri dishes (0.15 m in diameter) lined with filter paper (technical filter paper, 120 g/m²) moistened with specified concentrations of salt solutions, as mentioned in the previous paragraph. The control treatment consisted of filter paper moistened with distilled water. The germination test was conducted in a controlled germination chamber, set to an alternating temperature regime of 30°C for 16 h (light) and 20°C for 8 h (dark) over 10 d. At the end of this period, the final germination percentage was recorded, evaluating seedlings with normally developed essential structures.

Germinated seeds were observed and counted daily to determine the mean germination time (MGT). Seeds were considered germinated when the radicle had protruded at least 2 mm. Counts were recorded for each treatment group for 10 d. The calculation of MGT is done using the following formula:

$$MGT = \frac{\sum(n_i \times d)}{\sum n_i}$$

where n_i is the number of seeds that germinated every day, d = number of days from the beginning of the test.

The recovery of germination, salinity threshold, and critical salinity were defined and calculated according to Hu et al. (2018). To assess the recovery of germination, all non-germinated seeds subjected to various salt treatments (NaCl and Na₂SO₄) were placed in a medium moistened with distilled water for an additional 10 days following the initial ten-day germination period. The recovery of germination was determined using the following formula:

$$\text{Recovery of germination (\%)} = (a/b) \times 100$$

where a represents the number of re-germinated seeds after the transfer to distilled water, and b is the total number of non-germinated seeds in the salt treatments.

The salinity threshold is defined as the maximum salinity level at

which there is not a statistically significant difference in germination reduction compared to control. In contrast, critical salinity refers to the point at which germination is reduced by 50 %. To assess growth parameters, ten uniformly developed seedlings from each replicate were selected for measuring seedling root and shoot lengths and seedling leaf morphological characteristics (length, width and area). The shoot and root lengths were determined using a caliper. In contrast, seedling leaf measurements (length, width and area) were performed using a stereoscopic microscope STEMI 2000 with KERN camera and program for image analysis. Seedling leaf length and width were measured at the longest and the widest point of the leaf. Fresh weights of the shoots and roots were recorded using an analytical balance, and after drying the samples at 80°C until they reached a constant weight, the dry weights were measured (dry weight values for seedlings).

The Seed Vigor Index (SVI) was calculated according to the formula (Yaghoobian et al., 2022):

$$SVI = SDW / MGT,$$

SDW is the seedling's dry weight, and MGT is the mean germination time.

Salt Tolerance Index (STI) was calculated according to the formula (Khan et al., 2022):

$$STI (\%) = (SDW (\text{salt stress}) / SDW (\text{control})) \times 100$$

SDW is the seedling dry weight under salt stress and optimal conditions, expressed as a percentage.

2.3. Determination of relative water content (RWC)

Seedling leaves were initially weighed, placed in distilled water for an overnight soak, then dried and weighed again to determine their turgor weight. The samples were then dried at 80°C for 48 hours, and their dry weight was recorded. To calculate the relative water content, the following equation was used (El-Badri et al., 2021):

$$RWC = (\text{Fresh weight} - \text{dry weight}) / (\text{Turgor weight} - \text{dry weight}) \times 100$$

2.4. Proline quantification

The following procedure was employed to determine the proline content in fresh seedling shoots: A homogenate of 0.1 g of fresh shoots was prepared and mixed with 3 % aqueous sulfosalicylic acid. The mixture was then centrifuged to obtain a supernatant, mixed with glacial acetic acid and ninhydrin reagent. The resulting mixture was heated in a water bath for 30 minutes to facilitate the reaction. After heating, the mixture was allowed to cool and then centrifuged at 10,000 rpm for 5 minutes to separate the phases. The aqueous phase was extracted with 4 mL of toluene to isolate the chromophore. The absorbance of the toluene layer was measured at 520 nm using a UV spectrophotometer. Proline content was quantified by comparing the absorbance values to a standard curve established with known proline concentrations (Subramanyam et al., 2019).

2.5. Statistical analysis

A factorial completely randomized design was used for both the germination test and seedling growth analysis. A two-way ANOVA was conducted to evaluate the independent and interactive effects of salt type and concentration using PAST 4.11 (Hammer et al., 2001). Differences in measured traits between the two camelina genotypes were determined using Duncan's multiple range test at $P \leq 0.05$. Comprehensive univariate statistical analysis was performed to assess key growth and physiological parameters, including means, standard errors, coefficients of variation, and correlation coefficients. Linear regression

analysis and simple correlation (Pearson's correlation) were used to study correlations between relative water/proline content and selected morphometric data of seedlings.

3. Results

Both tested genotypes showed significantly different responses to salt type for several growth and germination parameters (Table of ANOVA is provided as supplementary file). However, salt concentrations had a consistently stronger effect on germination and growth traits across both genotypes, as indicated by its highly significant impact on all measured variables ($p \leq 0.01$). The interaction between salt type and concentration (ST \times C) showed statistical significance for shoot length, root length, and seedling dry weight in NS Slatka, while in NS Zlatka, it was significant for mean germination time, root length, and relative water content. These findings suggest that while salt concentration is the dominant factor influencing germination and growth, interaction effects between salt type and concentration resulted significant for some traits indicating a more complex response pattern for those parameters.

3.1. Seed germination variability in response to salinity stress

The results showed a gradual decrease in germination percentage with increasing salt concentration in both genotypes, with Na₂SO₄ exerting a more pronounced negative effect compared to NaCl (Table 1). In both genotypes in the presence of either salt types, germination percentage showed a marked decline at moderate salt concentrations (150 mM). Although NS Slatka followed a similar trend to NS Zlatka, it demonstrated a heightened sensitivity to NaCl at elevated concentrations (200 mM), leading to lower germination percentages. Correspondingly, mean germination time increased with salt concentration in both genotypes, showing that Na₂SO₄ significantly delayed germination more than NaCl, particularly at higher concentrations. Overall, both NaCl and Na₂SO₄ negatively impacted germination and prolonged germination time in a concentration-dependent way, with NS Slatka appearing more affected than NS Zlatka by salinity stress under high NaCl conditions.

The recovery germination of NS Slatka was higher under NaCl compared to Na₂SO₄. It exhibited a notable peak at 100 mM of NaCl, achieving approximately 62.4 %. However, germination recovery declined sharply at higher salt concentrations, dropping to 14.4 % at 200 mM NaCl. NS Slatka under Na₂SO₄ did not report any significant increase in recovery percentage compared to control (Fig. 1). NS Zlatka displayed an opposite behaviour, with a higher percentage of recovery observed after exposure to Na₂SO₄. This genotype achieved its highest recovery of germination at 150 mM for both salt types, reaching 45.4 % for NaCl and 56.5 % for Na₂SO₄, followed by a further decrease at 200 mM (35.4 % and 39.5 %, respectively) (Fig. 1).

Notably, NS Slatka appeared more sensitive to high salt concentrations, while NS Zlatka maintained relatively better recovery under higher NaCl and Na₂SO₄ levels. For both genotypes, the salinity threshold of germination appeared to be between 100 mM and 150 mM. (Fig. 2). Both genotypes likely reached critical salinity level at a concentration of 200 mM, independently of the types of salt. In NS Slatka, the reduction at this concentration was slightly higher (55.4 % for NaCl and 63.5 % for Na₂SO₄) compared with NS Zlatka (48.1 % for NaCl and 52.3 % for Na₂SO₄). As salinity concentration increased, both seed vigor index and stress tolerance index significantly decreased for both genotypes. For NS Slatka, under Na₂SO₄, the STI values were slightly lower than those of NaCl at each concentration, indicating a higher stress impact compared to NaCl.

3.2. Seedling morphometric responses to salinity stress

As salt concentration increased, both genotypes showed a consistent decline in most seedling growth parameters, including seedling shoot

Table 1
Seed germination and seedling growth traits of camelina in response to different concentrations of NaCl and Na₂SO₄. In the table mean value ± standard error are reported, and the coefficient of variation CV (%) is reported under brackets. Different superscript letters refer to different means in response to treatments ($P \leq 0.05$, Duncan's test).

Genotypes	Salt type	Treatment	Germination (%)	Mean germination time (d)	Seedling shoot fresh weight (g)	Seedling root fresh weight (g)	Seedling dry weight (g)	Seed vigor index SVI	Stress tolerance index STI
NS Slatka	NaCl	Control	91.33 ± 0.88 ^a (1.37)	1.83 ± 0.03 ^a (2.45)	0.0510 ± 0.0006 ^a (1.60)	0.0291 ± 0.0012 ^{ab} (5.83)	0.0077 ± 0.0003 ^a (5.30)	0.0042 ± 0.0002 ^a (5.96)	1.00 ± 0.04 ^a (5.30)
		50 mM	89.00 ± 1.15 ^b (1.83)	1.75 ± 0.08 ^a (6.36)	0.0501 ± 0.0005 ^b (1.45)	0.0310 ± 0.0003 ^{ab} (1.39)	0.0055 ± 0.0002 ^b (6.14)	0.0032 ± 0.0002 ^b (9.35)	0.719 ± 0.03 ^b (6.14)
		100 mM	87.33 ± 0.88 ^b (1.43)	2.67 ± 0.09 ^{bc} (4.71)	0.0439 ± 0.0005 ^{bc} (1.69)	0.0327 ± 0.0007 ^{bc} (3.01)	0.0028 ± 0.0002 ^d (11.93)	0.0010 ± 0.0001 ^c (16.26)	0.359 ± 0.03 ^c (11.93)
	Na ₂ SO ₄	150 mM	74.00 ± 0.58 ^d (1.10)	3.27 ± 0.04 ^{de} (1.66)	0.0353 ± 0.0005 ^d (19.56)	0.0244 ± 0.0062 ^{ef} (35.94)	0.0017 ± 0.0002 ^{ef} (14.39)	0.0005 ± 0.0001 ^{ef} (15.41)	0.225 ± 0.02 ^e (14.39)
		200 mM	40.67 ± 2.96 ^e (10.30)	5.48 ± 0.24 ^f (6.17)	0.0111 ± 0.0005 ^f (5.84)	0.0144 ± 0.001 ^f (10.31)	0.0013 ± 0.0001 ^f (12.75)	0.0002 ± 0.0001 ^f (15.95)	0.173 ± 0.02 ^f (12.75)
		Control	91.33 ± 0.88 ^a (1.37)	1.83 ± 0.03 ^a (2.45)	0.0510 ± 0.0006 ^a (1.60)	0.0291 ± 0.0011 ^{ab} (5.83)	0.0077 ± 0.0003 ^a (5.30)	0.0042 ± 0.0002 ^a (5.96)	1.00 ± 0.04 ^a (5.30)
NS Zlatka	NaCl	50 mM	87.00 ± 0.58 ^b (0.94)	2.30 ± 0.23 ^b (14.07)	0.0444 ± 0.0007 ^b (2.23)	0.0318 ± 0.0005 ^b (4.88)	0.0043 ± 0.0003 ^b (9.29)	0.0019 ± 0.0003 ^b (20.14)	0.563 ± 0.02 ^b (9.29)
		100 mM	82.00 ± 1.00 ^c (1.72)	3.05 ± 0.20 ^{cd} (9.30)	0.0391 ± 0.0005 ^{cd} (1.89)	0.0297 ± 0.0012 ^{ab} (2.56)	0.0022 ± 0.0002 ^{de} (9.48)	0.0007 ± 0.0001 ^{de} (16.80)	0.281 ± 0.02 ^{de} (9.48)
		150 mM	62.33 ± 1.45 ^d (3.30)	3.62 ± 0.06 ^e (2.19)	0.0234 ± 0.0004 ^d (2.45)	0.0264 ± 0.0004 ^{ab} (6.54)	0.0017 ± 0.0002 ^{ef} (12.58)	0.0004 ± 0.0001 ^{ef} (14.83)	0.212 ± 0.02 ^e (12.58)
	Na ₂ SO ₄	200 mM	33.33 ± 1.76 ^f (7.48)	4.73 ± 0.15 ^f (4.68)	0.0097 ± 0.0005 ^f (7.71)	0.0094 ± 0.0003 ^f (8.32)	0.0011 ± 0.0001 ^f (15.00)	0.0002 ± 0.0001 ^f (10.73)	0.147 ± 0.04 ^f (15.00)
		Control	88.00 ± 0.58 ^a (0.93)	1.70 ± 0.04 ^b (3.38)	0.0511 ± 0.0006 ^a (1.60)	0.0291 ± 0.0012 ^a (5.83)	0.0077 ± 0.0003 ^a (5.30)	0.0045 ± 0.0003 ^a (7.56)	1.00 ± 0.04 ^a (5.30)
		50 mM	88.67 ± 1.45 ^a (2.32)	1.51 ± 0.05 ^a (4.36)	0.0512 ± 0.0005 ^a (1.45)	0.0283 ± 0.0002 ^a (0.88)	0.0065 ± 0.0003 ^b (6.99)	0.0043 ± 0.0002 ^b (6.31)	0.844 ± 0.04 ^a (6.99)
NS Slatka	NaCl	100 mM	86.00 ± 1.00 ^b (1.64)	2.62 ± 0.07 ^c (2.50)	0.0486 ± 0.0007 ^a (1.95)	0.0274 ± 0.0016 ^{ab} (8.34)	0.0032 ± 0.0002 ^d (10.21)	0.0012 ± 0.0001 ^c (11.40)	0.420 ± 0.03 ^d (10.21)
		150 mM	69.67 ± 1.20 ^b (2.44)	3.32 ± 0.05 ^d (2.21)	0.0397 ± 0.0009 ^b (3.11)	0.0247 ± 0.0004 ^{bc} (2.50)	0.0023 ± 0.0001 ^{ef} (4.16)	0.0007 ± 0.0001 ^{de} (2.47)	0.294 ± 0.01 ^{ef} (4.16)
		200 mM	45.67 ± 3.48 ^d (10.78)	4.91 ^f ± 0.07 (2.14)	0.0184 ± 0.0005 ^d (8.85)	0.0134 ± 0.0003 ^d (3.01)	0.0017 ± 0.0001 ^f (5.44)	0.0004 ± 0.0001 ^e (6.36)	0.225 ± 0.01 ^f (5.44)
	Na ₂ SO ₄	Control	88.00 ± 0.58 ^a (0.93)	1.70 ^b ± 0.04 (3.38)	0.0511 ± 0.0006 ^a (1.60)	0.0291 ± 0.0012 ^a (5.83)	0.0077 ± 0.0003 ^a (5.30)	0.0045 ± 0.0003 ^a (7.56)	1.00 ± 0.04 ^a (5.30)
		50 mM	83.33 ± 0.67 ^a (1.07)	1.77 ^b ± 0.04 (3.48)	0.0510 ± 0.0005 ^a (1.40)	0.0296 ± 0.0012 ^a (5.83)	0.0056 ± 0.0003 ^b (8.86)	0.0032 ± 0.0001 ^b (11.92)	0.732 ± 0.05 ^a (8.86)
		100 mM	83.67 ± 0.33 ^a (0.56)	2.78 ^d ± 0.04 (2.26)	0.0446 ± 0.0017 ^b (5.39)	0.0290 ± 0.0011 ^a (5.21)	0.0026 ± 0.0002 ^{de} (12.04)	0.0009 ± 0.0001 ^{cd} (10.23)	0.333 ± 0.03 ^{de} (12.04)
NS Slatka	150 mM	62.67 ± 1.86 ^c (4.19)	3.55 ^f ± 0.04 (1.69)	0.0381 ± 0.0004 ^c (1.51)	0.0242 ± 0.0007 ^c (4.06)	0.0018 ± 0.0001 ^f (7.06)	0.0005 ± 0.0001 ^{de} (8.58)	0.229 ± 0.01 ^e (7.06)	
	200 mM	42.00 ± 1.53 ^d (5.14)	5.24 ^h ± 0.04 (1.21)	0.0183 ± 0.0005 ^d (4.13)	0.0112 ± 0.0010 ^d (12.44)	0.0010 ± 0.0001 ^g (12.07)	0.0002 ± 0.0001 ^e (12.72)	0.134 ± 0.01 ^g (12.07)	

and root length, shoot and root fresh weight, and seedling dry weight (Table 1). Notably, the negative impact of salt stress became more pronounced at higher concentrations, resulting in more severe reductions. For most parameters, NS Slatka demonstrated greater sensitivity to elevated Na₂SO₄ concentrations compared with NaCl, with significant declines observed at 100 mM of Na₂SO₄ and above. In contrast, NS Slatka at 50 mM and 100 mM for both salt types, reported root fresh weights higher than that of NS Zlatka. However, although NS Zlatka exhibited slightly lower growth parameter values under optimal conditions compared to NS Slatka, the degree of reduction in response to increasing salt concentrations was significantly lower when compared to the control. This observation suggested that NS Zlatka might have a greater capacity to withstand salinity stress compared to NS Slatka. Furthermore, in both genotypes Na₂SO₄ appeared to exert a more detrimental effect on morphological traits than NaCl, as evidenced by significantly lower fresh and dry weight values under Na₂SO₄ exposure, particularly at higher concentrations. When examining the seedling leaf dimensions, the data showed that both genotypes responded differently to increasing concentrations of salts. For NS Slatka, the leaf area remained stable or slightly increased with NaCl < 200 mM, while the leaf width increased at higher concentrations (1.77 mm), but the length remained relatively unaffected. In contrast, at 200 mM Na₂SO₄, all leaf surveyed traits (area, length, and width) decreased significantly, indicating greater sensitivity to Na₂SO₄. NS Zlatka showed a more consistent reduction in leaf area, length, and width with increasing NaCl, with a significant decrease in all traits at 200 mM (2.84 mm² area, 2.54 mm length, and 1.34 mm width). Similar reductions were observed at higher Na₂SO₄ concentrations, highlighting that NS Zlatka regarding leaf dimensions, overall, was more sensitive to salt stress compared with NS Slatka.

3.3. Changes in relative water content and proline levels in camelina seedlings

NaCl showed a more gradual decline in relative water content across increasing concentrations for both genotypes, especially in the 50–150 mM range (Fig. 3). Na₂SO₄ resulted in a steeper decline, particularly at 150 mM and 200 mM, suggesting that this salt has a stronger negative effect on this parameter compared to NaCl. While both genotypes show similar trends, NS Zlatka seems to maintain higher relative water content at lower salt concentrations, particularly in the Na₂SO₄ treatment. Both NaCl and Na₂SO₄ induced a significant increase in proline levels across various concentrations, indicating activated salt stress response in both genotypes (Fig. 4). As salt concentration increased, proline content raised in both genotypes, although the magnitude of this increase varied. NS Zlatka exhibited higher proline levels under salt stress compared with NS Slatka, particularly at higher concentrations (150 mM and 200 mM). While proline content consistently increased with the level of salt stress in both genotypes, their responses differ markedly. In NS Slatka, proline levels remained similar across both types of salt in control, low, and moderate salt concentrations (50–150 mM), but NaCl and Na₂SO₄ differed significantly at the highest concentration. Conversely, in NS Zlatka, proline levels showed a similar pattern in the two types of salt only at the highest salt concentration, indicating that the response to salt stress varies between the two genotypes under differing conditions. The correlation between different morphometric and physiological traits in the NS Slatka and NS Zlatka genotypes under salt treatment showed similarities as well as significant differences in their response to salt stress. For both genotypes, there was a strong positive correlation between seedling root length and weight (0.97 for NS Slatka and a similar value for NS Zlatka), indicating that root growth directly influenced root weight, suggesting that better root development under stress conditions may provide better tolerance to salinity. However, differences arose in the correlation between physiological traits like proline and water content. For both genotypes, proline content showed a negative correlation with root growth (length and

Table 2

Growth and morphometric traits of camelina seedlings in response to different concentrations of NaCl and Na₂SO₄. In the table mean value ± standard errors are reported, and the coefficient of variation CV (%) is reported under brackets. Different superscript letters refer to different means in response to treatments ($P \leq 0.05$, Duncan's test).

Genotypes	Salt type	Treatment	Shoot length (mm)	Root length	Leaf area (mm ²)	Leaf length (mm)	Leaf width
NS Slatka	NaCl	Control	35.18 ± 0.80 ^a (3.24)	40.49 ± 0.97 ^a (3.38)	3.71 ± 0.18 ^{ab} (15.7)	2.87 ± 0.07 ^{abc} (7.7)	1.60 ± 0.06 ^{ab} (12.1)
		50 mM	33.80 ± 0.83 ^a (3.46)	43.32 ± 0.66 ^a (2.14)	3.77 ± 0.22 ^{ab} (19.2)	2.72 ± 0.13 ^{bc} (15.8)	1.66 ± 0.11 ^{ab} (22.2)
		100 mM	29.57 ± 0.40 ^b (1.91)	32.90 ± 1.60 ^b (6.88)	3.63 ± 0.16 ^{ab} (14.2)	3.06 ± 0.07 ^a (7.9)	1.54 ± 0.03 ^b (7.6)
		150 mM	23.12 ± 0.57 ^d (3.48)	20.40 ± 3.52 ^d (24.39)	3.94 ± 0.17 ^a (13.9)	2.92 ± 0.07 ^{ab} (7.7)	1.69 ± 0.03 ^{ab} (5.9)
		200 mM	16.96 ± 0.89 ^e (7.44)	13.39 ^d ± 0.69 (5.05)	3.95 ± 0.3 ^a (21.3)	2.78 ± 0.08 ^{bc} (0.06)	1.77 ± 0.08 ^a (14.3)
	Na ₂ SO ₄	Control	35.18 ± 0.80 ^a (3.24)	40.49 ± 0.97 ^a (3.38)	3.71 ± 0.18 ^{ab} (15.7)	2.87 ± 0.07 ^{abc} (7.7)	1.60 ± 0.06 ^{ab} (12.1)
		50 mM	33.34 ± 0.52 ^a (2.19)	32.21 ± 1.49 ^b (6.55)	3.51 ± 0.17 ^{ab} (15.9)	2.85 ± 0.05 ^{abc} (6.0)	1.52 ± 0.05 ^b (11.0)
		100 mM	26.01 ^c ± 0.85 (4.62)	25.08 ± 0.98 ^c (5.53)	3.41 ± 0.13 ^{ab} (12.7)	2.67 ± 0.06 ^c (8.1)	1.54 ± 0.04 ^b (9.8)
		150 mM	21.78 ± 0.23 ^d (1.51)	17.16 ± 0.15 ^d (9.49)	3.24 ± 0.11 ^b (11.5)	2.65 ± 0.04 ^c (5.1)	1.5 ± 0.04 ^b (8.8)
		200 mM	13.97 ± 0.88 ^f (8.91)	16.16 ± 0.56 ^d (4.93)	2.5 ± 0.11 ^c (14.5)	2.4 ± 0.06 ^d (8.8)	1.32 ± 0.04 ^c (11.7)
NS Zlatka	NaCl	Control	33.68 ± 0.88 ^{ab} (3.68)	34.97 ± 1.00 ^a (4.03)	4.28 ± 0.13 ^a (9.96)	3.04 ± 0.06 ^a (6.8)	1.73 ± 0.04 ^a (7.7)
		50 mM	35.26 ± 0.44 ^a (1.78)	34.62 ± 0.68 ^a (2.76)	4.05 ± 0.19 ^a (14.9)	3.02 ± 0.03 ^a (3.7)	1.6 ± 0.04 ^{abc} (8.3)
		100 mM	26.43 ± 1.20 ^{cd} (6.41)	27.11 ± 1.10 ^c (5.74)	3.86 ± 0.20 ^{abc} (16.8)	2.99 ± 0.04 ^a (5.0)	1.57 ± 0.04 ^{abc} (9.9)
		150 mM	25.34 ± 1.32 ^{cd} (7.38)	24.06 ± 0.54 ^d (3.18)	3.29 ± 0.10 ^d (10.17)	2.66 ± 0.06 ^b (7.96)	1.48 ± 0.04 ^{bcd} (8.9)
		200 mM	16.67 ± 1.16 ^e (9.84)	14.23 ± 0.60 ^f (5.92)	2.84 ± 0.17 ^{cd} (19.7)	2.54 ± 0.07 ^{bc} (9.5)	1.34 ± 0.06 ^d (15.8)
	Na ₂ SO ₄	Control	33.68 ± 0.88 ^{ab} (3.68)	34.98 ± 1.00 ^a (4.03)	4.28 ± 0.13 ^a (9.96)	3.04 ± 0.06 ^a (6.8)	1.73 ± 0.04 ^a (7.7)
		50 mM	31.27 ± 1.52 ^b (6.89)	30.94 ± 1.11 ^b (5.09)	3.48 ± 0.17 ^{cd} (13.9)	2.65 ± 0.16 ^b (17.4)	1.65 ± 0.12 ^{ab} (22.2)
		100 mM	27.43 ^c ± 0.45 (2.32)	24.66 ± 1.27 ^{cd} (7.30)	3.75 ± 0.14 ^{bc} (12.0)	2.87 ± 0.03 ^a (6.2)	1.55 ± 0.03 ^{bc} (6.7)
		150 mM	23.73 ± 0.64 ^d (3.84)	18.06 ± 0.82 ^e (6.41)	3.1 ± 0.1 ^{de} (10.75)	2.60 ± 0.06 ^{bc} (7.7)	1.5 ± 0.03 ^{bc} (7.4)
		200 mM	15.95 ± 0.87 ^e (7.73)	13.83 ± 0.79 ^f (8.07)	2.65 ± 0.10 ^f (12.9)	2.42 ± 0.05 ^c (7.23)	1.35 ± 0.02 ^d (5.2)

Fig. 1. Recovery of germination of NS Slatka and NS Zlatka under varying salinity conditions. Different superscript letters refer to different means in response to treatments ($P \leq 0.05$, Duncan's test).

weight), suggesting that proline accumulation is part of a stress response associated with reduced organ growth, though this does not necessarily imply a direct inhibitory effect of proline on growth. For example, the negative correlation between proline and root length was -0.97 in NS Slatka and similarly expressed in NS Zlatka, indicating that proline accumulation acted as an osmotic stress response, reducing growth. Although both genotypes showed reduced growth due to proline accumulation, the water content in both showed a positive correlation with root traits, suggesting that better water retention contributed to root development, especially under saline conditions. However, there was a negative correlation between proline content and water content in both genotypes, indicating a connection between osmotic stress (through proline accumulation) and reduced water status. Regarding leaf traits, in NS Slatka, surface area, length, and width showed a strong positive correlation, suggesting a similar stress response. In contrast, NS Zlatka exhibited a significant negative correlation between leaf traits (surface area, length, width) and proline content. This negative correlation

suggested that higher proline accumulation in NS Zlatka may be linked to a reduction in leaf size and dimensions, indicating that saline stress affected leaf morphology in a way not observed in NS Slatka. Thus, NS Zlatka showed a different pattern of physiological and morphological adaptation to salinity, where proline accumulation was associated with reduced leaf growth, unlike in NS Slatka (Figs. 5 and 6).

4. Discussion

Germination represents a crucial developmental transition in a plant's life cycle, marked by the coordinated activation of various genetic and physiological activities. The process of germination primarily involves the imbibition of water, which activates the cells within the embryo in succession, leading to continued growth after a period of quiescence imposed during seed maturation (Wolny et al., 2018). However, any deviations from optimal conditions can significantly disrupt this delicate process. Different plant species exhibit varying

Fig. 2. Reduction of germination percentage (G%) and mean germination time (MGT%) for NS Slatka and NS Zlatka during germination under different levels of salt stress. Salinity threshold levels are circled in red.

Fig. 3. Relative water content of NS Slatka and NS Zlatka after exposure to different level of salinity stress. Different superscript letters refer to different means in response to treatments ($P \leq 0.05$, Duncan's test).

levels of stress tolerance at the various stages of growth, highlighting the importance of research in this area to understand and enhance germination success across diverse species. Evidence indicates that many oilseed species are particularly sensitive to the effects of salt in the soil, including *Brassica napus* (Batool et al., 2022), *Glycine max* (Nikolić et al., 2023), and *Helianthus annuus* (Ceccoli et al., 2022). Moreover, research on enzymatic antioxidant defense mechanisms, in both germinating seeds and field-grown plants, has shown that salt tolerance mechanisms observed in germinating seeds are largely reflected in the defense responses of mature plants, particularly in stress-sensitive species. During the germination phase, seeds exhibit sensitivity, which persists to some extent in the later growth stages of the plant (Nouripour-Sisakht et al., 2022).

At first glance, the results of the present research indicated an unequivocal linear influence of salt concentration on seed germination. However, a more thorough analysis of the tested parameters reveals significant deviations that suggest a far more complex relationship than initially apparent. The applied salt treatments significantly impaired germination and seedling growth performance of both tested genotypes, leading to delayed germination and decreased shoot and root development, with notable increases in mean germination time observed at moderate salt concentrations (150 mM). These results contradict Morales et al. (2017), who stated that camelina seeds can germinate without disturbance and produce robust seedlings at concentrations of 300 mM NaCl; however, it should be noted those authors tested three specific varieties of camelina—Blaine Creek, Cheyenne, and

Fig. 4. Proline content of NS Slatka and NS Zlatka seedlings after exposure to different level of salinity stress. Different superscript letters refer to different means in response to treatments ($P \leq 0.05$, Duncan's test).

Fig. 5. Pearson's coefficient of variation between selected examined traits of NS Slatka in different concentrations and types of salt, ($P \leq 0.05$) crossed (sl: shoot length, rl: root length, sw: shoot fresh weight, rw: root fresh weight, pc: proline content, rwc: relative water content, la: leaf area, ll: leaf length, lw: leaf width).

Suneson—selected for their high biodiesel potential, which might account for the differences observed in salt tolerance. Furthermore, the results on germination percentage and mean germination time suggested that camelina was significantly affected by salinity stress, with Na_2SO_4 being more detrimental than NaCl, and the genotype NS Zlatka being slightly more tolerant than NS Slatka under high salinity levels. When considering the germination process under saline conditions, it is important to take into account the facts that: I) salts bind water molecules, preventing imbibition and obstructing the normal progression of germination and the initial growth of seedlings (Acosta-Motos et al., 2017); II) insufficient water availability in high-salinity conditions results from salt impact on soil structure and chemical processes, which also hinders nutrient uptake (Korres et al., 2016); III) seeds and seedlings are often subjected to the toxic effects of salt ions they absorb, which disrupt regular metabolic processes (Zhang et al., 2015). The result of our study indicates that increased salts strongly inhibit the germination process of camelina. The pronounced recovery germination peak, for

both NS Slatka and NS Zlatka, at 100 mM NaCl and for NS Zlatka at 100–150 mM Na_2SO_4 suggested that those genotypes can recover from moderate levels of different types of salt stress, requiring further investigation into the mechanisms underlying these differences in salinity tolerance. Future research could also contribute to a better understanding of the relationship between salt tolerance defense mechanisms in germinating seeds and specific physiological traits involved in mature plant responses to salt stress. Namely, according to Nouripour-Sisakht et al. (2022) in comparative testing, germinating seeds and mature plants of fennel (*Foeniculum vulgare* Mill.) had a higher ability to tolerate salinity, while all anise (*Pimpinella anisum* L.) genotypes showed sensitivity to salt stress at both stages due to insufficient antioxidant defenses, ionic homeostasis and osmoprotective measures. Further, the significantly higher germination recovery of NS Zlatka after exposure to the highest concentration of salt indicated its more promising response to emphasized salinity stress conditions. At the same time, the high germination recovery rate (exceeding 40 % for both genotypes

Fig. 6. Pearson's coefficient of variation between selected examined traits of NS Zlatka in different concentrations and types of salt, ($P \leq 0.05$) crossed (sl: shoot length, rl: root length, sw: shoot fresh weight, rw: root fresh weight, pc: proline content, rwc: relative water content, la: leaf area, ll: leaf length, lw: leaf width).

under 150 mM of the tested salt types) indicated that salinity only has a temporary effect on camelina seed germination. The metabolism of germinating seeds and seedlings involves the transformation of storage proteins and fatty acids into carbohydrates. This process slows down in the presence of salt but can be rapidly reactivated when favourable conditions for recovery arise (Debez et al., 2018). This can be related to the principles of seed priming, a widely used technique in which seeds are exposed to various often unfavorable agents, activating specific physicochemical reactions that enable the primed seeds to respond more quickly and effectively to stress (Méndez et al., 2016). An example is haloprimering, where seeds are treated with low concentrations of different salts, enhancing their germination potential once the salt stress is removed (Wojtyła et al., 2016, Purwestri et al., 2023).

The capacity for rapid recovery when seeds are relocated from stressful to less stressful conditions is crucial for maintaining crop stability and resilience. This adaptability could be a key strategy for camelina to thrive in moderate saline environments, representing a favorable characteristic especially in soil where rapid salinity fluctuations are present. In these cases, when water availability is low and salinity is high, seeds can experience stress, possibly due to osmotic stress or ion toxicity (Hadjadj et al., 2023). The high rate of germination recovery reported by camelina, especially NS Zlatka, suggested that, when optimal conditions are restored, seeds could ensure a satisfactory crop establishment. During this study, since the seeds and seedlings were subjected to short-term exposure to stress, it is more likely that osmotic stress and inadequate amount of water—resulting from the presence of salt—were the primary factors affecting their growth, rather than ion toxicity. At the same time, Hadjadj et al. (2023), in their examination of safflower seeds' response to salinity stress, found that this species can tolerate salt concentrations of up to 400 mM for Na_2SO_4 and up to 500 mM for NaCl. They noticed that reduced germination and growth resulted from osmotic effects and ion toxicity, leading them to identify safflower as a promising species for rehabilitating saline soils. Besides, their study demonstrates that safflower has a high level of recoverability, as it is able to germinate in water even after being exposed to high levels of salinity. The results also showed that increasing the concentrations of both NaCl and Na_2SO_4 negatively affected the growth of camelina seedlings in both genotypes, leading to a significant decrease in the seedling dimensions, including leaf dimension, shoot and root fresh weight, of and dry weight of seedlings. Considering that roots play a key role in water and nutrient absorption (Yan et al., 2023), any impairment of root function can significantly hinder overall plant growth. In this study, increasing salinity levels resulted in a gradual

decline in organ elongation, as evidenced by the shorter lengths of both roots and shoots. Notably, root length was more severely impacted than shoot, likely because roots are more directly exposed to salinity for longer periods. The root growth decline is attributed to both toxicity and restricted nutrient and water uptake due to osmotic stress (Ouji et al., 2015). Moreover, Na_2SO_4 demonstrated a more harmful effect on root growth compared with NaCl, especially at higher concentrations. Interestingly, the NS Zlatka showed slightly better tolerance, particularly in terms of seedling length under Na_2SO_4 conditions, suggesting it may have enhanced tolerance in saline environments. This was supported by STI values, which is an important indicator for assessing the overall effectiveness of varieties in various environmental conditions (Barpete et al., 2015).

The morphometric traits of seedlings revealed different trends. The leaf, being a primary organ for photosynthesis and transpiration, is particularly sensitive to environmental stress, with salinity often causing the earliest visible symptoms (Läuchli and Grattan, 2007). Reduced leaf growth is widely recognized as a key indicator of a plant's tolerance to salinity (Chen et al., 2014; Avestan et al., 2021), and our findings align with this. Specifically, a more pronounced reduction in leaf dimensions in the NS Zlatka under saline conditions was observed, indicating lower salt tolerance compared to NS Slatka, which maintained a more stable leaf size. This suggests that NS Slatka may have adaptive mechanisms to better preserve leaf function and structure under stress. At the same time, NS Slatka was more sensitive to the influence of Na_2SO_4 than to NaCl, whereas the opposite trend was observed in NS Zlatka. Studies by Mohammed et al. (2021) and Palchetti et al. (2021) similarly noted increased leaf width in salt-tolerant genotypes as an adaptive trait, potentially reflecting heritable characteristics for tolerance in saline environments. Likewise, Yao et al. (2023) found that low salt concentrations enhance leaf growth in *Lycium barbarum*, likely due to long-term adaptation to salt stress. Our results showed that with rising NaCl levels, leaf width in NS Slatka increased, mirroring these adaptive responses. This highlights a broader strategy among genotypes to maintain growth in saline conditions, suggesting potential for breeding salt-tolerant plants that retain essential growth and functional traits in saline soils. Monitoring relative water content is important for understanding the physiological state of seedlings and their ability to cope with salinity, as it represents the amount of water in plant tissues relative to their water-holding capacity. In the present study, the relative water content in seedlings significantly decreased at a concentration of 150 mM for both salt types and genotypes. Various researchers have observed that relative water content decreases with higher salt stress in different crops,

including rice (Polash et al., 2018), pea (Khan et al., 2022) and barley (Boussora et al., 2024).

Proline accumulation in NS Slatka under Na₂SO₄ started from 100 mM onward, despite the osmotic stress highlighted by RWC decrease from the lowest concentration of salt; while, under NaCl, proline increased from the lowest concentration of salt. This suggests that Slatka under Na₂SO₄ initially relies on ion homeostasis or other osmotic regulation mechanisms rather than osmoprotectants synthesis, such as Na⁺/K⁺ transport, and only engages proline synthesis at higher stress levels. However, the early accumulation of proline in this genotype under NaCl resulted to be an effective defense against osmotic stress at low to moderate salt concentration, as suggested by the stable RWC reported at these NaCl levels.

In contrast, NS Zlatka showed early proline accumulation at the lowest concentration of both NaCl and Na₂SO₄, indicating an early osmotic adjustment mechanism under both salts, leading to a better stabilization of cellular structures and maintenance of turgor pressure (El Moukhtari et al., 2020, Ghosh et al., 2022), as confirmed by stable RWC at moderate concentration of both salts.

This effective early response to osmotic stress under NaCl in NS Slatka and under NaCl and Na₂SO₄ in NS Zlatka aligns with findings in fennel (Gholami Zali and Ehsanzadeh, 2022), where exogenous proline accumulation was associated with better osmotic regulation under salt stress.

Exceeding 150 mM of both salts, in both genotypes RWC sharply decreased, although a relevant proline accumulation, suggesting the presence of oxidative cell damages, as observed by Ibrahimova et al. (2025) testing the same salt concentration in wheat. Therefore, these findings confirm at high salt concentrations what stated by Hannachi and Van Labeke. (2018), which argue that elevated proline levels under stress merely indicate stress presence rather than directly contributing to improved responses to salt stress, contrary to the assertion by Abdelrady et al. (2024) that proline is essential for mediating plant defense against osmotic stress and enhancing adaptation and tolerance to unfavorable salinity. Additionally, proline metabolism is crucial for seed germination, as it supports the oxidative pentose-phosphate pathway, which generates NAD(P)⁺, which plays a central role in the initiation of the germination process (Bailey., 2019). The negative correlation between germination and proline content under salt stress indicated a high stress level during the germination process, suggesting that proline synthesis serves as a defense mechanism.

5. Conclusion

The present study examined the salt tolerance of two camelina genotypes under varying salinity levels and salt types. The observed differences in responses across salt types, their concentrations, and the tested genotypes underscore the complexity of interactions between seeds, salt, and soil. Salinity levels above 150 mM significantly reduced most seedling growth parameters, indicating that both genotypes have a tolerance threshold below this value. Sodium sulfate was found to be more harmful than sodium chloride. NS Slatka was more sensitive to salt regarding germination and seedling growth but demonstrated greater stability in leaf dimensions, suggesting potential adaptive mechanisms. Proline accumulation was higher in NS Zlatka, particularly under Na₂SO₄ stress, suggesting that this genotype may employ more efficient mechanisms to cope with salt stress. Both genotypes showed strong germination recovery, with NS Zlatka displaying a higher recovery rate, suggesting camelina suitability for salt affected areas in which salinity fluctuations are present. Overall, this study emphasizes the importance of genotype-specific approaches for breeding salt-tolerant camelina varieties and highlights the need for a deeper understanding of salt stress effects on germination to develop more resilient crops.

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CRediT authorship contribution statement

Jelena Ovuka: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Formal analysis. **Jelena Jocković:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Dušica Jovičić:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Zorica Nikolić:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Conceptualization. **Rossella Mastroberardino:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Investigation. **Federica Zanetti:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Conceptualization. **Ana Marjanović Jeromela:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Resources, Investigation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Marjanovic Jeromela Ana reports financial support was provided by Horizon Europe Excellent Science. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.indcrop.2025.120773](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.indcrop.2025.120773).

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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